

Exploring Mathematical Reasoning and Math-Talk Through Izak9

Gráinne Higgins

St. Philomena's N.S., Tullamore

This paper focuses on the use of Izak9 in promoting the development of mathematical reasoning and Math-Talk in an Irish classroom. Recent national and international assessments have shown many positive results in relation to the mathematical learning of Irish pupils (Shiel et al., 2014; Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). However, the skill of reasoning is a relative weakness among this cohort (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). Reasoning is highlighted as one of the four 'elements' of the proposed new Primary Mathematics Curriculum (PMC), which is currently under development (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA), 2016; NCCA, 2017). This study was qualitative in nature. The research methods utilised were focus group interviews and observations of mathematics lessons. Findings of this study demonstrated that mathematical reasoning skills were promoted in Izak9 lessons, specifically the exploration of patterns and the justification of mathematical processes and solutions. In addition, a Math-Talk environment was also supported through the use of the resource.

Introduction

The aim of this research was to explore the development of mathematical reasoning skills and the use of Math-Talk through the use of Izak9 in an Irish sixth-class classroom. The research has been drawn from a larger study in which the overarching research question was: What are the learning experiences created through the use of Izak9? This paper will focus on two of the emerging sub-questions: Can mathematical reasoning skills be developed through the use of Izak9?; To what extent can a Math-Talk environment be promoted through the use of Izak9?

The use of Izak9 was central to this research. Izak9 consists of a set of 27 cubes which can be separated into three sets of nine cubes to be used as sets in small groups in primary and early post-primary mathematics education. There are colours, numbers and other mathematical symbols and notations on the faces of the cubes (see Figure 1). Mathematical tasks to be used alongside the cubes are available through user login (Izak9, n.d.). The online user area contains a selection of tasks based on the number, algebra, shape and space and data handling.

Figure 1

Illustration of Izak9 cubes

This research comes at a time of curricular change in mathematics, with the development of the new PMC underway (NCCA, 2016). This time of transition offers an opportunity to research the mathematical learning experiences of Irish primary school pupils under the current Primary School Mathematics Curriculum (PSMC) (Department of Education and Skills (DES), 1999a), prior to the implementation of a new curriculum.

In recent years, there have been many positive results relating to Irish pupils' mathematical performance in both national and international assessments. The National Assessment of Mathematics and English Reading (NAMER) assesses Irish second class and sixth class pupils in four content areas (number and algebra, shape and space, measures, data) and five processes (understand and recall, implement, reason, integrate and connect, apply and problem solve). In the 2014 NAMER, significant improvement was noted in the performance of sixth class pupils in all content areas and processes when compared with 2009 results (Shiel et al., 2014). Irish pupils also performed significantly above the scale centrepoint for mathematics in the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). However, the TIMSS assessment outlined that the skill of mathematical reasoning is a relative weakness at both sixth class primary and second year post-primary levels. This research, therefore, sought to investigate pupils' use of mathematical reasoning through the use of Izak9. It also sought to explore how the use of Math-Talk may contribute to the development of this skill.

Literature Review

Mathematical Reasoning

Mathematical reasoning is listed as one of six skills that should underpin the five strands of the PSMC (DES, 1999a). The following features of mathematical reasoning resonate with this current research and will be explored: search for and investigate mathematical patterns and relationships; justify processes/results of mathematical activities, problems and projects (DES, 1999b, p. 69). Reasoning is also highlighted as one of the key elements of mathematical learning included in the proposed new mathematics curriculum (NCCA, 2017). In parallel with the PSMC, emphasis is placed on justification of mathematical processes, as well as the use of logic and generalisation of mathematical ideas.

Stein et al. (2008) describe an approach which enables mathematical reasoning through the use of collaborative learning and discussion. This model encourages learners to develop reasoning skills. Pupils work on a mathematical problem in a small group, before re-engaging with the whole class to discuss their work. The group work enables discussion and negotiation of the problem at hand in whatever way pupils see fit, in the knowledge that they may later share their solution with the group. On return to the whole class group there is still scope for further reasoning to occur. Different groups may bring different perspectives to the problem. Groups should be invited to outline their solutions or strategies, but may also be subjected to counter statements by teachers or peers. In these instances, groups must use logic to justify their case. This reasoning process enables the development of deep mathematical understanding through the use of negotiation, justification and generalisation. The success of

a lesson such as that outlined by Stein et al. (2008) is dependent upon the engagement of the learners involved. The use of discussion, or Math-Talk, is central to this engagement.

Math-Talk

Math-Talk describes the use of discussion in explaining mathematical thinking, in an effort to support and extend learning (Chapin et al., 2009; Hufferd-Ackles et al., 2004; NCCA, 2016). The PSMC, although not referring specifically to Math-Talk, highlights the importance of talk and discussion in mathematics (DES, 1999a). A key aim of the PSMC is “to enable the child to use mathematical language effectively and accurately” (DES, 1999a, p. 12). Mathematical language includes content-specific mathematical vocabulary, but also incorporates the communication and expression of “mathematical ideas, processes and results in oral and written form” as well as the ability to “reason, investigate and hypothesise with patterns and relationships in mathematics” (DES, 1999a, p. 12). Further emphasis on the strategy of talk and discussion has been recommended in an Irish context (Dooley et al., 2014; NicMhuirí, 2012).

Through the effective development of a Math-Talk environment in the classroom, mathematical discourse can stretch beyond a tool simply for teacher evaluation. It can become exploratory territory whereby students can create shared understanding through consideration of the opinions of others and the revision of their own opinions (Wells and Arauz, 2006; NicMhuirí, 2012). With practice and teacher interaction, pupils should become more adept at refining their mathematical language (Wells & Arauz, 2006; Davis et al., 2010). Through the modelling and promotion of effective Math-Talk, teachers can facilitate learning activities which encourage students to reason mathematically. In particular, to explain, reflect and justify their thinking in mathematics.

Izak9

As a relatively new resource, there is limited research available into the use of Izak9 in mathematical teaching and learning. However, the research and reports that exist outline benefits associated with its use (Education Authority of Northern Ireland (EANI), 2016; Cantley et al., 2017). In Izak9 tasks, students participate in activities as part of a group, exploring and investigating possible responses to questions posed. An EANI report (2016) outlined the benefits of this in terms of collaboration and the students’ engagement in learning. Following an intervention in using Izak9 as part of mathematics, the report showed a significant increase in “thinking skills and personal capabilities through collaborative/ peer learning” (p.3). Izak9 cubes aim to promote shared learning experiences (EANI, 2016; Cantley et al., 2017). Communication between learners in groups and in the whole class also improved significantly in the EANI study. The learning that is intended to take place through the use of Izak9 lends itself to the promotion of Math-Talk in the classroom. Students are given the opportunity to discuss the learning tasks in their groups and with the class, while teachers may act as facilitators to this (Cantley et al., 2017). Teachers are encouraged to use questioning to promote mathematical reasoning and discussion around the tasks. The significant development of the skill of communicating mathematically through the use of

Izak9 (EANI, 2016) lends itself to current and proposed Irish mathematics curricula, as communication is noted as a mathematical skill as well as an element in the PMC (DES, 1999a; NCCA, 2017). For the purpose of this study, Izak9 will therefore be explored in relation to the promotion of Math-Talk and the development of mathematical reasoning.

Methodology

The participants involved in this qualitative research were sixth class pupils attending an all-girls DEIS school in an Irish town. For this research, non-probability purposive sampling was used. This form of sampling is advantageous to small-scale research as it is less complicated and less costly to carry out (Cohen et al., 2011). There were 25 girls in the class, aged from 11 to 13. Ethical procedures were followed in line with Dublin City University (DCU) guidelines. The DCU Institute of Education Ethics application form was completed and approved prior to beginning research. Following this, informed consent was acquired by the school principal, board of management and parents. Children who had received parental/guardian consent to participate in the research were given a plain language statement in the form of a letter and an assent form. These outlined in child-friendly language what the research entailed, assuring that participation was voluntary.

The research methods utilised were focus group interviews, as well as the observation of six mathematics lessons in which Izak9 was the main resource in use. The lessons took place once a week over a six week period. Focus group transcripts and observational field notes from lessons were used as the primary data for the research.

For the Izak9 lessons, the class was split into six groups with four to five pupils in each. Two of these groups also took part in focus group interviews. These groups were interviewed twice in a semi-structured format - once before the Izak9 lessons commenced, and again after all six Izak9 lessons were completed. Questions were included in the interview schedule under the headings: experience of learning maths; group work; Math-Talk and reasoning. The class were observed in six mathematics lessons using Izak9. Each lesson lasted approximately one hour and the format of the lessons reflected the structure of that outlined by Stein et al. (2008). During each lesson, observational notes were recorded, detailing the events and interactions taking place. These notes served as a basis for more detailed field notes to be developed and analysed. Following each focus group interview and Izak9 lesson, the resulting data was reviewed and emerging themes were noted. After the lessons and focus groups were completed, all of the data was read thoroughly. Codes were assigned to data which was relevant to the area of research and which recurred throughout the data. The codes which emerged were then categorised in order to develop themes. These themes were: mathematical reasoning through Izak9; constructivist and social constructivist learning facilitated by Izak9; pupil engagement with Izak9; the use of Math-Talk in the classroom environment. All themes were explored in the resulting thesis. For the purpose of this paper, the themes of mathematical reasoning and Math-Talk are explored.

While great consideration was given to the design of this research, it is not without limitations. When using non-probability purposive sampling, it is important to highlight that

data and results arising cannot claim to be representative of the wider population (Cohen et al., 2011).

Findings and Discussion

For the purpose of this paper, three of the six Izak9 lessons carried out in the larger study will be explored in addressing the research questions: Can mathematical reasoning skills be developed through the use of Izak9?; To what extent can a Math-Talk environment be promoted through the use of Izak9? The following subsections will outline mathematical reasoning and Math-Talk that took place during Lesson 1 and Lesson 2 ('3x3 Demo' and 'Odd One Out') and Lesson 4 ('Magic Square').

3x3 Demo' and 'Odd One Out'

In '3x3 Demo' and 'Odd One Out' the pupils were instructed to build walls based on the first nine multiples of three and the first nine prime numbers (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

Multiples of three and prime numbers using Izak9 cubes

After the walls were built by the pupils, they were prompted by the teacher to discuss the patterns they could see on the walls. There was a heavy focus on simple patterns of colour and number. For example, in '3x3 Demo', it was observed that the even numbers form a 'diamond' shape and the odd numbers form an 'X'. The background shapes were also observed to form a pattern – circle, square, circle, square.

Some observations made in these lessons were inaccurate examples of patterns, as can occur in the initial stages of a Math-Talk environment (Davis et al., 2010; Wells & Arauz, 2008). For example, in the lesson 'Odd One Out', the top row had the numbers 2, 3 and 5. It was suggested that this was a pattern as 5 is the sum of 2 and 3. However, upon questioning it was agreed that as this does not continue on the other rows it is not considered a pattern. One participant looked at the difference between consecutive numbers on the wall in an attempt to discover a pattern. In this instance, through prompted continuation of her method, she discovered that this also did not seem to be a pattern. Prompts for justification by the teacher in such instances were an important component of the Math-Talk taking place, as referenced by Hufferd-Ackles et al. (2004).

It was observed that the majority of productive Math-Talk in both of these lessons occurred in the whole class segment at the end of each activity. At this point, refinement and further exploration of strategies was encouraged. This promotes the development of Math-

Talk skills from exploratory and imprecise to more coherent and accurate (Davis et al., 2010; Wells & Arauz, 2008). Lucy felt that this was a beneficial step in the learning process. “Afterwards the whole class had a big discussion on like what we did... I feel like that helped the most”. The lesson ‘Odd One Out’, provided an example of such discussion. The class was asked to make the number 20 with two numbers, using subtraction only. The numbers available were 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23. This problem was solved with relative ease by all groups ($23 - 3 = 20$). However, in the whole class discussion, a student questioned if this was the only solution. This was put to the rest of the group who proceeded to discuss their thoughts. It was concluded that as 23 is the highest available number and you must subtract, it is the only number you can begin with. For this reason $23 - 3 = 20$ is the only possible solution. Pupil questioning here promoted the Math-Talk environment outlined by Hufferd-Ackles et al. (2004), and represented a move away from teacher-led learning to an environment in which pupils took responsibility for their own learning experiences. While the initial question was perceived as ‘easy’, through the use of effective Math-Talk, reasoning skills were further developed by facilitating a whole-class discussion after the task.

‘Magic Square’

In the lesson ‘Magic Square’, the pupils were asked to build a 3x3 wall in which all of the rows, columns and diagonals added to the same number. After the task was completed, the class looked at the solutions of each group and reflected on these. Many observations were recorded with regards to the patterns of odd and even numbers in rows, columns and diagonals (see Figure 3). This led to speculation surrounding combinations of numbers that will give odd and even numbers. Again, in this instance, the pupils began to guide the direction of their learning. One participant wondered if there was a way of making 15 with just even numbers.

Figure 3

Sample of pupil observations in ‘Magic Square’

This statement prompted an investigation by the class, in which the groups sought to prove or disprove the theory that it was impossible to make 15 using three even numbers. As part of this investigation, the class agreed that this theory was in fact correct. Through their work, they also discovered a generalised pattern regarding the sum of odd and even numbers. They deduced that the sum of two even numbers is always even, the sum of two odd numbers is always even, and the sum of an odd and even number is always odd. One pupil drew a comparison between this generalised pattern and something she had learned in maths earlier in the week. She wondered whether addition patterns of odd and even numbers were similar

to the multiplication pattern of integers. Through examination of these general patterns, she observed similarities in their structure (see Figure 4 and Table 1).

Figure 4

Sample pattern exploration by participant

As the Izak9 lessons progressed, observations of patterns became a part of the reasoning process, furthering the pupils' ability to complete tasks and create opportunities for further learning. In '3x3 Demo' and 'Odd One Out' participants made simplistic observations based on the Izak9 walls. In 'Magic Square', the pupils began to seek out, explore and justify more complex patterns, at times leading to generalisations of mathematical ideas.

Conclusion

The research explored in this paper utilised qualitative research methods to explore the development of mathematical reasoning and Math-Talk skills through the use of Izak9. This research was particularly appropriate given the current development of the new PMC (NCCA, 2016; NCCA, 2017). The findings of this research demonstrated how Izak9 may be used to promote a Math-Talk environment in which the discussion of mathematical thinking can support and extend learning. In addition, the nature of this Math-Talk became more refined as the lessons progressed. The findings also demonstrated pupils' mathematical reasoning through the investigation of mathematical patterns. This observation began in an exploratory manner with simplistic patterns relating to colour and number observed. However, throughout the course of the Izak9 lessons, this developed into the formation of generalised patterns and relationships. This research was carried out on a small scale and therefore cannot claim to be representative of the wider population (Cohen et al., 2011). While there was not the scope in this paper to explore alternative mathematical resources to promote reasoning, this is an area that may warrant further research. In addition, educators should be provided with suitable continuous professional development (CPD) in the transition from the current PSMC to the new PMC, so as to address the shortcomings in current practice as highlighted in relevant studies (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020).

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